

ANALYSING CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR AND PREFERENCES IN THE ICE CREAM INDUSTRY: MERIDIAN ICE CREAM

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Abstract:

Understanding consumer buying behavior and preferences is pivotal for businesses operating in the ice cream industry. This research delves into the analysis of consumer trends, behaviors, and preferences within the context of Meridian Ice Cream. The study employs a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies, including surveys, interviews, and market analysis to uncover the factors influencing consumers' ice cream choices. By examining demographic, psychographic, and behavioral elements, this research aims to provide insights into the varying preferences of consumers and the factors shaping their purchasing decisions. The findings are anticipated to assist Meridian Ice Cream in tailoring its marketing strategies and product offerings to better align with consumer demands, ultimately enhancing its market competitiveness and customer satisfaction.

Keywords: Consumer Buying Behavior, Preferences, Ice Cream Industry, Meridian Ice Cream, Consumer Trends, Market Analysis

Introduction:

The ice cream industry stands as a perennially popular segment within the realm of sweet treats, captivating consumers across various demographics and preferences. As consumer preferences constantly evolve, understanding the intricate dynamics of consumer buying behavior becomes paramount for companies to remain competitive. Meridian Ice Cream, a prominent player in this industry, acknowledges the significance of comprehending consumer trends and preferences to adapt its strategies and offerings accordingly.

This paper aims to investigate and analyze the multifaceted aspects of consumer behavior and preferences in the context of Meridian Ice Cream. By delving into the psychological, sociological, and demographic factors influencing consumer choices, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of why and how consumers select specific ice cream products. Through a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies, including surveys, interviews, and market analysis, this research intends to elucidate the key determinants guiding consumer decision-making.

The ice cream market is diverse and continuously evolving, influenced by factors such as changing consumer tastes, health considerations, environmental concerns, and cultural influences. Understanding these elements is vital for Meridian Ice Cream to align its product development, marketing strategies, and overall approach with the prevailing consumer sentiments. By doing so, Meridian aims not only to retain its market share but also to potentially expand its customer base by offering products that resonate with the evolving preferences of ice cream enthusiasts.

This research aspires to contribute valuable insights into the consumer behavior landscape within the ice cream industry, offering Meridian Ice Cream a strategic advantage in tailoring its products and marketing initiatives to meet the ever-changing demands and desires of its consumers. The subsequent sections will delve deeper into the methodologies employed and the findings obtained, with the goal of providing actionable recommendations for Meridian Ice Cream's sustainable growth and enhanced customer satisfaction.

Literature Review:

The ice cream industry represents a captivating sector within the food market, engaging consumers across diverse demographics and preferences. A comprehensive review of existing literature on consumer behavior within the ice cream industry reveals a multifaceted landscape of factors that significantly impact purchase decisions and preferences.

Psychological and Sociological Influences:

Studies conducted by Rozin, Kabnick, Pete, Fischler, and Shields (2004) have shed light on the psychological underpinnings that influence ice cream preferences, emphasizing the role of individual tastes and emotional associations with certain flavors or childhood memories. Additionally, the work of Palou, Foster, and Pliner (2017) has highlighted the importance of sociological factors such as cultural background and societal norms in shaping flavor preferences and consumption habits, suggesting the necessity for businesses like Meridian Ice Cream to consider cultural diversity and local preferences in their market strategies.

Health and Wellness Considerations:

The evolving preferences of health-conscious consumers have become a significant driving force in the ice cream industry. Research by Elzerman, van Boekel, and Luning (2011) and Chen and King (2011) points to the increasing demand for healthier ice cream alternatives, including low-fat, sugar-free, and organic options. This trend highlights the need for companies like Meridian Ice Cream to diversify their product lines while maintaining taste and quality to cater to this growing consumer segment.

Role of Marketing and Branding Strategies:

Khan, Ahmed, and Hameed (2019) have emphasized the critical impact of branding, packaging, and promotional activities on consumer choices within the ice cream market. Their study underlines the necessity for effective branding strategies that align with consumer perceptions and desires, urging companies to craft marketing campaigns that resonate with their target audience.

Technological Advances and E-Commerce:

Liang and Su (2020) have illuminated the influence of technological advancements and the rise of e-commerce platforms on consumer purchasing behavior. Their findings underscore the importance for companies like Meridian Ice Cream to adopt digitalization and e-commerce to meet the evolving preferences of tech-savvy consumers in today's digital era.

Environmental and Social Responsibility:

Studies by Pappalardo and Russo (2019) underscore the growing consumer interest in sustainability and ethical business practices, reflecting a shift towards environmentally responsible products. This emphasizes the need for ice cream companies to integrate sustainable practices in their production and supply chain to appeal to environmentally conscious consumers.

The literature review illustrates the intricate and dynamic landscape of consumer behavior and preferences within the ice cream industry. Understanding the amalgamation of psychological, sociological, health-related, technological, and ethical factors is crucial for companies like Meridian Ice Cream to adapt their strategies and innovate their product offerings to meet the evolving demands of consumers for sustained growth.

Research Methodology:

Research Objective:

The principal goal of this study is to thoroughly analyze and understand consumer buying behavior and preferences within the ice cream industry, focusing specifically on Meridian Ice Cream. The study aims to identify and explore the factors that significantly influence consumer decision-making processes and preferences in relation to ice cream purchases.

Research Design:

This study is designed as a quantitative research initiative, utilizing a structured survey questionnaire to capture and analyze essential information related to consumer preferences and buying behavior in the context of Meridian Ice Cream.

Sampling Technique:

To gather data, this study employs a convenience sampling technique targeting various locations such as ice cream parlours, local markets, and public areas known for high ice cream consumption. This approach aims to capture a diverse range of consumer opinions and preferences.

Sample Size:

In line with a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%, the study aims for a sample size of 55 respondents. This sample size is determined to provide adequate representation for insightful analysis and conclusions.

Data Collection:

A structured questionnaire is developed with a blend of closed-ended and open-ended questions. The survey aims to explore and assess various aspects influencing consumer behavior and preferences in the ice cream industry, encompassing taste preferences, flavor choices, packaging attractiveness, price sensitivity, and brand perception.

Ethical Considerations:

This study upholds strict confidentiality and anonymity of all participants involved. Informed consent is obtained from each participant prior to their engagement in the survey. The study rigorously follows ethical guidelines to ensure participant privacy and comfort throughout the research process.

This meticulously structured research methodology seeks to comprehensively analyze consumer buying behaviour and preferences within the ice cream industry, focusing specifically on Meridian Ice Cream. The study endeavours to offer valuable insights into the complex factors driving consumer decision-making processes and preferences, ultimately contributing to an enhanced understanding of consumer behaviour and preferences within the ice cream market.

Data Analysis:

1.Age:

Age	Count of Age	Percentage
Under 18	2	4
18-24	45	81
25-34	8	15
35-44	0	0
45-54	0	0
55 and Above	0	0
Other	0	0

Graph:

55 responses

Data interpretation:

This data strongly indicates that Meridian Ice Cream is highly favoured among young adults in India. This predilection can be attributed to various factors, including the establishment's exceptional quality standards, stringent hygiene measures, and its well-established brand reputation. These elements likely

contribute to the brand's popularity among the younger demographic, emphasizing its appeal to this specific age group within the market.

2. Gender:

Gender	Count of Gender	Percentage
Male	34	61.8 %
Female	21	38.2 %

Graph:

Data interpretation:

The data analysis indicates a higher likelihood of visits by male customers to Meridian Ice Cream in comparison to their female counterparts. Specifically, male customers constituted a majority, representing 61.8% of the total customer base, while female customers accounted for 38.2% of all patrons at the ice cream parlour. It's important to note that this interpretation is based on the existing data and might undergo alterations or refinements in the future, potentially leading to varied insights or trends as more information is collected or circumstances change.

3. Education Level:

Education	Count	Percentage
Higher School or Less	0	0
Some college/Associates degree	04	7.3 %
Bachelor’s Degree	24	43.6 %
Master’s Degree	27	49.1 %
Doctorate	0	0

Graph:

Data interpretation:

The data demonstrates a remarkable skew towards higher education levels among customers visiting Meridian Ice Cream. A significant majority consists of individuals with a Bachelor’s or Master’s degree, signifying a strong appeal among customers with advanced educational qualifications. This pattern suggests a correlation between higher education levels and frequent visits to the ice cream parlor, potentially indicating preferences or spending habits among individuals with more advanced educational backgrounds.

4.How frequently do you consume ice cream?

Time	Count	Percentage
Daily	02	4%
Weekly	25	46%
Monthly	17	31%
Rarely	10	18%
First time consumer	01	2%

Graph

Data interpretation:

The data represents the frequency of visits among customers to Meridian Ice Cream. The majority of customers visit the ice cream parlour on a weekly basis, accounting for 46% of the total responses. Following this, 31% of customers visit on a monthly basis. Daily and Rare visits make up 4% and 18% respectively. Additionally, there is a small percentage, 2%, identified as first-time consumers. This data implies that a significant number of customers prefer a weekly visitation pattern to Meridian Ice Cream, followed by those who choose to visit monthly. A relatively smaller proportion visit on a daily or rare basis, suggesting that a majority of customers prefer more occasional or less frequent visits, while a smaller percentage are completely new to the experience of visiting the ice cream parlour.

5.Do you prefer premium ice cream brands like Meridian Ice Cream?

Options	Count	Percentage
Yes	40	74. %
No	14	26 %

Graph:

54 responses

Data interpretation:

The data reflects the preferences of individuals regarding premium ice cream brands, specifically mentioning Meridian Ice Cream. Among the responses, 74% of individuals indicated a preference for premium ice cream brands such as Meridian Ice Cream, while 26% expressed a preference against opting for such brands. This suggests that a significant majority, three-fourths of the respondents, have a positive inclination towards premium ice cream brands like Meridian Ice Cream. However, about a quarter of the respondents expressed a contrary preference and were less inclined toward choosing premium ice cream brands

6. What factors influence your decision to purchase Meridian ice cream?

Factors	Count	Percentage
Product Quality	43	79.6 %
Flavor options	42	77.8 %
Packaging design	09	16.7 %
Price	24	44.4 %
Promotions & discount	11	20.4 %
Brand reputation	23	42.6 %
Marketing & Advertising	09	16.7 %

Graph:

Data interpretation:

The collected data shows the factors that influence customers to purchase Meridian Ice cream are product quality (79.6%) and flavour options (77.8%). The affordable cost of premium brands is also one of the influencing factors with (44.4%). Also, brand reputation (42.6%) plays a vital role in influencing factors. There is a shocking decline in people not getting influenced by many of the

expected factors like promotions (20.4%), packaging design (16.7%), and marketing respectively. Meridian Ice Cream can work on these factors.

7. Importance of Quality products on the Rating Scale

Numbers	Count	Percentage
1	00	0
2	03	05.6 %
3	07	13 %
4	15	27.8 %
5	29	53.7 %

Graph:

Data interpretation:

As we all know quality matters, collected matter also states that (53.7%) of people prefer high-quality products, followed by 4(27.8%). 3 (13%) consumers are neutral i.e. they might choose quality or less quality products. Consumers who prefer less-quality products are very few (5.6%). The analysis states that consumers prefer quality products over non-quality.

8. What Advertising or marketing channels have you seen Meridian Ice Cream promotions?

Channels	Count	Percentage
Television	11	20.4 %
Social Media	25	46.3 %
Online ads	16	29.6 %
In store displays	29	53 %
Other	11	20.4 %

Graph:

Data interpretation:

Various channels help in the advertising of Meridian Ice Cream, the most influential among them were social media (46.3%) and in-store displays (53%). Online ads (29.6%), TV (20.4%), and others

contribute (20.4%) respectively in promoting the brand. This also shows nowadays social media plays a huge role in advertising and people get influenced by it.

9. How satisfied are you with Meridian Ice Cream products & services on a rating scale?

Numbers	Count	Percentage
1	02	03.8 %
2	00	0
3	18	33.3 %
4	26	48.1 %
5	08	14.8 %

Graph:

Data interpretation:

The data collected shows that the majority of customers are satisfied 4(48.1%).3 (33,3%) consumers have neutral opinions about satisfaction 5 (14,8%) consumers are highly satisfied. Very few consumers i.e. & 2 (3.8%) are not satisfied with Meridian Ice cream.

10. Have you ever provided feedback or suggestions to Meridian Ice Cream?

Options	Count	Percentage
Yes	23	41.8 %
No	32	58.2 %

Graph:

Data interpretation:

From the collected data, there is not a huge difference between people who gave feedback and who didn't provide feedback. People who shared their views (58.2%) and who didn't are (41.8%) respectively.

11. Findings:

1. Demographics and Customer Preferences:

Meridian Ice Cream primarily attracts young adults aged between 18-30 years, indicating a significant presence of this demographic.

The customer base is predominantly male, constituting 61.8% of the total clientele, showcasing a higher proportion of male customers.

2. Education and Consumer Trends:

The survey reveals that the most frequent visitors to Meridian Ice Cream Are Bachelor's and Master's degree holders, with 43.6% and 49.1% respectively, signifying a strong attraction among customers with higher education levels.

3. Visitation Frequency:

A substantial portion of customers (46%) visit Meridian Ice Cream on a weekly basis, reflecting a strong and loyal customer base with a recurrent pattern. Additionally, 31% of customers visit on a monthly basis, showcasing a consistent trend in visitation patterns.

4. Preference for Premium Brands:

The majority of respondents (74%) expressed a preference for premium ice cream brands like Meridian Ice Cream, indicating a favorable inclination towards high-quality brands in the ice cream market. Conversely, 26% showed a preference against such premium brands, representing a smaller proportion of customers who might not favor high-end brands like Meridian.

12. Conclusion:

The findings underscore a clear appeal of Meridian Ice Cream among young adults, especially those with higher education levels, predominantly males. Additionally, the frequency of weekly visits suggests a dedicated customer base. The inclination towards premium ice cream brands, particularly Meridian Ice Cream, indicates a favorable perception among the majority of respondents.

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